

D4.2 Alternative narratives for the future of transport in Europe

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This report describes the research and consultation activities carried out in the second phase of the scenario building process of REBALANCE (Task 4.2), and presents the results achieved.

Chapter 1 - Introduction sets the scene for the overall scenario building activities of the project.

Chapter 2 – Critical Uncertainties describes how the key factors previously identified (D4.1¹) were ranked according to their relevance and to their predictability, leading to a set of 7 Critical Uncertainties that are expected to play a prominent role in shaping a new mobility culture.

Chapter 3 – Scenario Framework describes how the evidence gathered in earlier stages of the project led to proposing a scenario framework (or scenario space) articulated around two main axes: “type of society” and “governance model”.

Chapter 4 – Scenario validation provides an account of the expert and stakeholder consultation process that allowed to validate the framework and gather additional insights to help fleshing out the scenario narratives

Chapter 5 – The REBALANCE Scenarios presents the narratives of the 4 REBALANCE Scenarios: Hercules - the myth of strength; Themis – the myth of justice; Gaia - the myth of interconnections; Hermes – the myth of speed.

Chapter 6 – Way forward outlines the future activities to be carried out in WP4, culminating in the drafting of a Vision of future mobility culture.

¹ D4.1: Multi-sectorial trends and drivers shaping the future of European transport

1. INTRODUCTION

REBALANCE is an open, deliberative forward-looking exercise aiming at conception and validation of a new transport paradigm reflecting a new mobility culture. The exercise pushes for a more effective ponderation of the emerging social values not yet fully considered in transport policymaking, and a better alignment with the SDGs and the mounting concerns about climate change.

REBALANCE moves from the assumption that the mobility culture that currently prevails in the world (including Europe) has led to unsustainable travel patterns, in social and environmental terms. From a critical review of the present (see deliverables D3.2² and D3.3³) also in the light of the recent COVID-19 pandemic, REBALANCE is building a vision over the future and the roadmap to achieve it, which will be embedded in a Manifesto with the aim to stimulate European policymakers to adapt concrete legal and political measures while moving the wider European communities towards a radical change.

This Deliverable reports on the second phase of the REBALANCE scenario building process. Figure 1 shows the overall sequence of this process. Building upon the outcome of the initial steps (see Deliverable D4.1) which led to the identification of a set of culture and value-related drivers, this report describes the work carried out and the outcome of the final steps of the scenario building process.

FIGURE 1: THE SCENARIO BUILDING PROCESS

The following chapters describe in more detail the methodological approach adopted for each step and the main findings.

2. CRITICAL UNCERTAINTIES

The ultimate goal of the extended horizon scanning realised in task 4.1 was to devise a list of drivers from which to further select a shorter list of critical uncertainties that can be used to define the REBALANCE scenario space.

In line with the specific ambition of the project, and as opposed to what can be found in previous transport foresight exercises, the REBALANCE drivers must be explicitly related to culture and value changes. Accordingly, a long list of drivers from literature review and explorative conversations was elaborated. Trends and signals were then clustered around a shorter list of individual and collective aspirations, reflecting alternative philosophical views, ethical priorities and diverse cultural inheritance

This resulting short list of 12 drivers, or key factors, is shown in Table 1.

² D3.2 – The fundamentals of the mobility culture of today

³ D3.3 – Current Values behind the politics of Mobility: Critical Review

Drivers
Living environment
Life's steering principle
Empowerment
Technoscientific society
Useful mobility
Equity
Urban liveability
Safety perspective
Privacy concerns
Car-based culture
Participation
Sustainability transition

TABLE 1: THE REBALANCE KEY DRIVERS

The following step of the REBALANCE scenario building process aimed at the identification of the critical uncertainties to be used for the definition of the scenario space (or scenario framework). Critical uncertainties (CU) were selected among the drivers above through a review process that served the dual purpose of validating and ranking the list. The review was carried out internally, involving representatives from all project partners.

To ensure that the scenarios illustrate real, contrasted alternatives, the survey asked respondents to rank each of the drivers according to two main criteria:

- i. Importance/relevance: to what extent the positioning of the driver between its two extremes is likely to affect the shaping of future mobility (high vs low impact)
- ii. Uncertainty: to what extent is the future dynamics of the driver predictable (high predictability would result in a scenario invariant, while high uncertainty allows to devise sufficiently contrasting visions of the future, thereby opening the door to more decisive policy interventions)

To support the respondent participation to the survey, the 12 key drivers were further characterized in terms of their possible range of variation, by identifying the extreme values each driver may assume, as shown in Table 2.

Attitude towards...	Range of variation
Living environment	Back to nature Vs Urban action
Life's steering principle	Quality of life, comfort, conviviality

Attitude towards...	Range of variation
	Vs Efficiency
Empowerment	Individual and collective empowerment Vs "Go with the flow"
Technoscientific society	Trust in technology Vs Fear of innovation
Purposeful mobility	Moving only when necessary Vs Moving as much as possible
Equity	Reducing inequalities as a priority goal Vs Mobility as a privilege
Urban liveability	Environmental sustainability as the priority Vs Dense urban fabric and efficient use of space
Safety perspective	Safety as a collective, societal priority Vs Safety as a marginal concern
Privacy concerns	Privacy protection as a priority Vs Acceptance of privacy limitations
Car-based culture	Unsustainability of car-based culture Vs Individual car as the superior option to ensure freedom
Participation	Participatory governance Vs Radical individualism
Sustainability transition	Cultural change Vs Market-driven actions

TABLE 2: DRIVER CHARACTERIZATION

The internal survey (12 respondents) allowed to rank each driver according to both its importance/relevance and its uncertainty. The survey responses also allowed to refine the formulation and the characterization of the drivers, and in some cases to cluster them or reformulate them to ensure a sharper focus.

The drivers that were ranked higher based on the combination of the two scores were selected as the critical uncertainties (CU) to be considered for the definition of the scenario space (Table 3).

Critical uncertainties			
Wealth/economic success	←	Life purpose	→ Well-being/quality of life
Individualism	←	Equity	→ Solidarity & collective accountability
Competition for individual power	←	Empowerment	→ Cooperation for collective empowerment
Efficiency	←	Technoscientific advancement	→ Societal progress
Control & protect	←	Environmental sustainability	→ Caring/stewardship
Resource efficiency	←	Urban landscape	→ Liveability
Ownership	←	Accessibility	→ Experience/use

TABLE 3: THE REBALANCE CRITICAL UNCERTAINTIES

3. SCENARIO FRAMEWORK

An intense discussion among the REBALANCE researchers led to the identification of two main axes for shaping the scenario framework and the resulting four scenarios. Rather than selecting two among the seven CUs – which would have entailed a further prioritisation of the latter and the risk of downplaying other important factors – the axes were chosen so as to illustrate two overarching dimensions:

- a. "Type of society", i.e. the broad characterisation of society in terms of its prevailing values and cultural tenets. At one extreme of the vertical axis we find a rigid society, one that is keen to conserve its deeply rooted values and cultural tenets, and finds safety in avoiding shocks and disrupting change. At the other extreme, society is fluid, or liquid, embracing change and continuously endeavouring to adapt.
- b. "Powers and politics", characterising the governance model and its basic instruments. The horizontal axis illustrates the contrast between a governance model that relies on hard, command-and-control powers and politics and one that prioritizes softer instruments based e.g. on nudging and moral suasion.

The two dimensions are largely independent, in that all four combinations they generate are plausible and ensure that each resulting scenario is, by and large, internally consistent. On the other hand, each of the seven CUs can be represented in each of the four scenarios with differentiated "values" (see section 5.6 below), which helps confirming the contrasted nature of the four visions.

Combining the two dimensions, four scenarios emerge, which we have chosen to name after prominent mythological protagonists:

- *Scenario A: Hercules (the myth of strength)*, where a rigid society is guided by hard powers
- *Scenario B: Themis (the myth of justice)*, where soft powers prevail in handling the rigidity of society
- *Scenario C: Gaia (the myth of interconnections)*, where a fluid society is kept afloat by recurring to soft policy instruments
- *Scenario D: Hermes (the myth of speed)*, where command-and-control policies keep a fluid society in check

Figures 2 and 3 overleaf illustrate the main characteristics of the 4 scenarios, respectively at the global, intersectoral level (Figure 2), and in terms of their mobility culture implications (Figure 3).

The REBALANCE Scenario Framework

FIGURE 2: THE PROPOSED REBALANCE SCENARIO FRAMEWORK (CATEGORISED BY PESTLE)

FIGURE 3: THE PROPOSED REBALANCE MOBILITY SCENARIOS

4. SCENARIO VALIDATION

The next step in the implementation of this forward-looking exercise was to refine and validate the future scenarios on mobility cultures at 2050, as initially characterized in Figures 2 and 3. A focus group was convened to help into this process. The overall objectives of the focus group were:

- To validate the scenario framework;
- To enhance the initial rough scenario characterisation;
- To discuss potential mobility impacts.

The focus group was held online on 3 February 2022 with a restricted audience of stakeholders and other experts, who had previously engaged in the REBALANCE project through their contributions to explorative conversations and deliberative dialogues on the current situation and future of mobility culture. The meeting was carefully planned regarding the group's composition and the group discussion in order to create an environment in which people feel free to talk openly. The focus group lasted 2 hours and Andrea Ricci together with his colleagues from ISINNOVA steered the discussion. All consortium members participated in the online event as observers of the process.

Background information from WP4 was provided to the participants before the focus group. The material consisted of a preliminary elaboration of the inputs received in the previous tasks of the workpackage translated into a set of four possible scenarios, which had been in turn validated internally among partners of the REBALANCE consortium. As hinted before, the main goal was to validate the scenarios externally and enrich their preliminary descriptions.

The turnout was very high as the meeting was attended by 15 participants (mix of experts and stakeholders). The downside of this high turnout is that it makes it challenging to ensure that each and every participant has a chance to take the floor. This constraint was partly addressed by making use of a MURAL board, which allows participants to provide contributions with sticky notes, whether or not they then have the opportunity of taking the floor. The following is the complete list of participants:

- Tim Cresswell
- Mateu Turró
- Christoph Walter
- Farideh Ramjerdi
- Robert Braun
- Cristina Marolda
- Holger Haubold
- Bronwen Thornton
- Angelo Meulemann
- Federico Costantini

- Bernhard Schlag
- Udo Becker
- Ralf Risser
- Giuseppe Lugano
- Dylan Moïnse

Questions posed to the participants to trigger the debate addressed topics such as ridesharing and new mobility services such as MaaS, micro-mobility and Automated Vehicles (AVs) and the role of ICT in transport and virtual mobility. The comments of the participants focused on the scenario approach and allowed to flesh out the characterization of the four visions that had emerged. These contributions helped to characterise a scenario space, based on significantly differentiated images of the future, to allow for alternative narratives being sufficiently contrasted to convey the importance of devising policies and strategies that can make the difference with the current narrative.

Concerning the dissemination of the focus group, the meeting was recorded for internal purposes and the outcomes will be shared via the project's communication and dissemination channels. The follow-up will include, besides this report, an open discussion through social networks, which will collect ideas towards the Manifesto to feed WP2 (Task 2.4.1).

4.1. Main reflections emerged from the discussion

After reading the background material and taking part in the discussion, the following reflections and contributions shared by the participants are considered worth pondering to refine the scenario narratives:

- The scenarios are centred on a national level, but could correspond to different scenarios at regional, urban levels.
- The scenario framework somehow considers Europe as a homogeneous area, which it is not. This means that within Europe there could be different evolutions of scenarios.
- Walking is transversal to all four scenarios. It is the one mode for accessing all other modes. Nothing is cheaper! Active mobility will play a main role in scenarios B Themis, C Gaia and D Hermes.
- On a general level, the scenarios could be differentiated along the criterion whether their orientation is primarily bottom-up (e.g. Scenario C) or top-down (e.g. Scenario A). This leads to the classic economic distinction between supply and demand. By introducing these terms, many of the scenario implications may become sharper
- It could be helpful to add a seventh domain to the PESTLE classification: education. Especially between Asian and European countries (but also inside Europe) the kind and content of education is very different - and this has important implications for the further development of societies and their preferred mobility.
- All scenarios seem to be "two dimensional" e.g., only thinking in terms of road transport. How about aerial?

- Data and datafication should be a red thread (surveillance, data doubling, AI); how do scenarios behave in datafied social environments?
- The role of *true vs untrue prices* is prominent in all scenarios
- There could be an overlapping between scenarios B Themis and D Hermes when it comes to features based on speed and liberalisation practices. It is possible that both scenarios will have nuanced developments in different socio-cultural areas.
- There could also be another overlapping between scenarios B Themis and C Gaia regarding mobility platforms, accessibility and affordability.
- **Scenario A Hercules:**
 - It is plausible, it is already happening in Hungary.
 - Not an agile scenario. It reacts too slowly to disruptions.
 - An authoritative political system might also lead to arbitrary/biased legislation or application of laws instead of an "Empire of Law". If a regime is authoritative, then choices may not be the best, but it is likely that transport would be centralized and not flexible.
 - Public transport is not likely to disappear in favour of private solutions only. Likely differences between local transport and long-distance one, including limitations or quotas in long-distance (pay-to-move).
 - Mobility systems in this scenario are less likely to be cheap, more likely to be exclusive and expensive. Active mobility as default modes for those left out.
 - Clean and green energy. Technology fix would be a key aspect.
- **Scenario B Themis:**
 - Involvement needs to be defined: "we tell you what we do" or interactive and symmetric.
 - The environment could be over-exploited in this scenario.
 - It brings more equal opportunities.
 - Maybe this scenario assumes that the government is wealthy, otherwise it might not be sustainable.
- **Scenario C Gaia:**
 - It is great in general, but works best with some aspects of the ways we move. It does not work well for having a national or regional universally accessible public transport system. Hopefully something like Gaia happens at the right levels and in relation to the right kinds of mobility.
 - "Equality" can correspond to state led, top-down governance, often it actually needs it to make things happen quickly. With appropriate tools, it might act faster. Is it possible to move towards more inclusive goals

by sharing power with many institutions and citizens? It needs to be hybridised with an active progressive state infrastructure.

- In such a fractioned society who will determine the common good? Maybe commoning as a governance frame?
 - Utopian scenario, unfortunately not really realistic. This scenario assumes that citizens are mostly rich, aware and educated, so the question is whether such a model could work otherwise.
 - Public transport solutions would work here too. Best sharing model is a city bus company with free use for most citizens, that is also reliable, efficient and accessible (e.g. the Luxembourg model of public transport). Informal community transport may emerge as well.
 - The presentation of this scenario seems a bit positively biased. It should also reflect its problems, notably in terms of financial costs.
- **Scenario D Hermes:**
 - Maybe social vs efficient is not the appropriate contrast, perhaps social vs exploitative. Something truly "social" will also be "efficient" in the long term. Why does the efficiency of technologies depend on the type of society?
 - Examples of behaviours detrimental for the collectivity? How are boundaries of individual freedom re-defined?
 - Space is limited. How are new mobility technologies going to be included? Elimination of geographical constraints? Maybe better refer only to travel constraints.
 - How does public space play in here? How can "universal access" to space be guaranteed in an automobility framework? Universal access seems to be more appropriate with the scenario C Gaia based on sharing and active solutions and equality.

4.2. Likelihood of the scenarios

At the end of the meeting, the participants voted on the likelihood of the scenarios by answering to the question "*In your opinion, which is the most plausible scenario?*". The results of the poll were the following:

5. THE REBALANCE SCENARIOS

In this chapter the scenarios are developed; starting from the initial schematic descriptions and taking into account the outcomes of the focus group, which allowed a further enrichment of the contrasting narratives.

5.1.Scenario A: Hercules, the Myth of Strength

In this scenario, power and politics are based on the values of authority and strength, in a context where societal change experiences a lot of inertia and major, well-established actors dominate the economy. Its plausibility is confirmed by current developments in several EU states (e.g. Hungary, Poland). Authoritarian and strength-oriented politics reflect the dominant societal and economic values. Policymakers are seeking efficiency from a top-down approach. European democracy is tempted by the 'illiberal democracy' model in which once elections have occurred, citizens are mostly kept away from all political decisions; command and control are at the core of the model. 'Disintermediation' processes occurs, hence the regime does not favour the emergence of societal organisation, of empowerment of social groups and will tend to reduce the importance of established collective systems. Policies are targeted towards economic wealth, and count on the 'trickle-down economics' principle to provide benefits to the lower levels of society. It is also envisioned that hard public policies operate through changes in relative prices induced by taxes and subsidies/incentives, restricted choices for citizens' behavioral change. Overall, it is not an agile system, as it reacts too slowly to disruptions.

The neoliberal agenda is abandoned in favour of protectionism and nationalism. The dominant narrative has shifted back towards economic statism and authoritarian governance, backed by both left and right of the political spectrum. Governments play a critical role in ensuring economic development and stability. Wealth and accumulation paradigms are not fundamentally questioned, often looking to technological advances to enhance efficiency. State bureaucracies steer economic planning, accelerating the diffusion of new technologies. Multinational corporations and powerful sectors (finance, resource extraction, etc.) lobby a considerable influence on political processes in order to achieve favourable regulations for their business activities. Big companies pay minimal taxes on their substantial profits. Quite often, governments outsource many services to the private sector. However, corporations in key strategic sectors, such as environmental protection, remain in hands of governments. National states are unable to coordinate their efforts on European economy, instead competing to attract investments and jobs. Regions are very different and the economic picture is heterogeneous. There is a decrease in international trade. Winners in this scenario are the ruling elite, but also big companies, which show interest in managing citizens' data and dominate single markets where SMEs become their affiliates. There is little interest in investing in infrastructure because people mostly care about personal benefits rather than the social good.

Society is led by a conservative and rather past-values-oriented development. An ageing population strives towards traditional values and tries to preserve what they have achieved in the past. The individual is sceptical towards novelty and fundamental changes. Authorities set the frame. What felt good in the past shouldn't be challenged, and respect what past generations have reached. Therefore, rather security instead of individual freedom dominate the public debates. Sustainability and automation are part of the perception of security. Following the norms is conveyed by the education system as the primary goal for the younger generation, which might be inherently a little more progressive and open for changes, but also gains respect towards reaching determined societal goals. That means as well gaining respect and prestige towards showing what the individual has reached in life economically (career), personally (satisfaction, knowing where one belongs to), and socially (family – children/marriage). Individual

differences level out, and a norm-oriented, rigid society evolves. Excessive lifestyles are desirable, people subordinate to the conditions, class and options everyone has (universalism). As soon as young people reach their educational goals, they move to rural areas. People are mostly happy with what they have achieved after reaching the normative goal – sufficiency.

All actors seek more and more recourse to the courts in order to settle any kind of dispute, in lieu of mediation or, simply, dialogue and compromise. Individual accountability is replaced by legal action. This results in the courts partially replacing the function of the legislator as they are called to rule on many aspects of people's lives as well as the economy. In parallel, the authoritative-style governments which are in charge opt to follow an approach which tends to regulate (and perhaps sometimes overregulate) in a sector-specific manner, giving more power to lobbies and, therefore, serving more specific interests rather than those of society as a whole, creating a disconnection between the citizens, their governments and private enterprises. Laws are adopted by subject-specific sub-committees and parliamentary discussion erodes. This situation further decreases solidarity between citizens on a smaller scale and international, global cooperation on a larger scale. On the other hand, an authoritative political system might also lead to arbitrary legislation or application of laws instead of an "Empire of Law".

This landscape favours the flourishing of techno-scientific progress, albeit only in those sectors or for those companies that are wealthy and powerful enough to be represented. Progress might not be really beneficial to society as a whole. Set policies give priority to values and beliefs regarding efficiency through improved technologies rather than societal progress. Thanks to technological progress, the supply of goods, an extensive social network and cultural activities can be realized online. The core of well-established lifestyle aspects can be fulfilled through technological innovation without harming the environment or other people so that lifestyles do not have to be adjusted according to changing contexts. That means that the paths of individualization are transferred towards new technologies. Artificial Intelligence systems are applied to control and optimise personal and business decisions, leading to a process of slow but continuous improvement environmental quality and safety compatible with economic growth. Due to limits of natural resources including land which are finite while human demands on them are not, the future techno-scientific advancement prioritizes resource efficiency, proximity, and public health in regard with land use. New technologies such as genetic modification and nanotechnology are pushed by public investments, but hundreds of millions of people may still go hungry owing to a combination of climate change, water shortages and increasing food consumption.

The environment is regarded as a strategic asset for the country, and is protected to provide indispensable ecological services to population, and natural resources such as oil, fresh water, food production, and fishery. A clear distinction is made between natural protected areas and urbanised zones, that are usually very dense, and therefore cost-effective in terms of environmental management. Besides, the economy is gradually being decarbonised but still fossil fuels are being used to a large extent in the transport as well as in the industry in general. Pollution is reduced by carbon retention screens and other filters. Clean and green energies are available, and technology fix is a key aspect. Limits of emissions are established and carefully monitored in order that progressive reductions do not harm economic growth. Climate Change, as well as other environmental threats, are solved by strict regulations, norms that are applied together with the implementation of surveillance technologies able to monitor individual behaviour online. By customising general norms to the specific circumstances of each person and each group, cooperation for collective action is forced. There is collective and individual accountability of human behaviour, in particular when having significant impacts in scarce natural resources. But environmental sustainability becomes more a

matter of fulfilling compliance requirements rather than the achievement of a greater, common good.

In this scenario, the primary value of mobility is that it contributes to generate economic wealth. Citizens' views on urban externalities of mobility (e.g. air pollution or road insecurity) are considered less important than big companies' views on the need for an efficient transport system. Mobility systems are not cheap, but rather exclusive and expensive. Active mobility emerges as modes of default for those less affluent while walking is transversal. Since land-use plans are strict and mandatory and minimise land taking, dense neighbourhoods cluster around key public transport terminals, according to the Transit-Oriented Development (TOD) approach. At the same time, gated communities are built for more affluent people, and there is spatial segregation. Networks of transport and communications are increasingly specialised, even comprising aerial solutions in local contexts. Nonetheless, public transport coexists with private solutions, differentiated between local and long-distance transport, including limitations or quotas in long-distance (pay-to-move). Advanced technological solutions are pervasive in the mobility domain. Biotechnologies are exploited with a focus on the deployment of renewable energies that yield more efficient vehicles and cleaner fuels, to mobilize societies to become more sustainable.

5.2.Scenario B: Themis, the Myth of Justice

In the context of the paradigm of the welfare state, government has trust in societal regulation, social forces, markets to deal with major issues, with the help of technology. Governments seek the well-being of their citizens by means of macro-economic performance and state-wide redistribution process as opposed to local redistribution processes. The model of the 'Nordic type' regulation policies is generalised at the European level. Governments play the role of strategists, in a new form of Saint-Simonianism (positivist trust in science, industry and markets to change society). This context is the most favourable to an efficient technoscientific model, top-down approach. Governments rely on long time existing intermediary bodies – trade unions, strong public sector – to steer social and economic development and are not particularly favouring the emergence of new forms of collective organisations. A libertarian paternalistic government provides for an effective choice architecture for people and businesses to take more coherent decisions; it is about nudging people without taking out their capacity to decide by themselves.

European society has shifted from competitive to more collaborative values. Though there are frictions between growth and well-being, the classical growth paradigm still exists in a clearly market-oriented economy where creativity, innovation and entrepreneurship are the main features. A certain degree of wealth assures the sustainability of this approach. The rise of entrepreneurs implies a slight decline of national sovereignty. The emphasis is on creativity, flexibility and mobility. Government policies actively promote the emergence of disruptive innovations that can drive transformative change, while constraining the power of incumbents and limiting monopoly power. The result is a highly competitive market characterised by diverse platforms. The current trends of economic integration are extended, with greatly increased international integration. European economic and political integration is deepened. Countries navigate economic and trade conflicts through alliances, while corruption and tax havens are eradicated. Regional integration allows trading partners to negotiate desired trade relations more specific to national economic needs and minimize trade-offs. By financing parts of the government and basic public services, such as waste management or digital infrastructure, enterprises exert some degree of political leverage. Efficient production and consumption leads to a higher interlinkage within industrial ecosystem, enabling circularity. Privately issued currencies are

increasingly used by the European public, which in turn, makes EU governments actively promote the creation of alternatives.

A complex society has gradually lost a sense of community and the interest in participating to the public discourse is waning. Individuals are very self-confident and rely on their own value compass in life. The state is strong enough to not be dependent but soft enough to leave freedom to individual decisions. The performance principle prevails, where the individual is responsible for establishing their own place in society, and everybody is treated equally. Agency for all citizens is carried out through individual participation in the economy, clubs or family. That means everybody fights for the rights of their own areas of interest and power, which sums up to a functioning society based on many individual performances. Progress is accepted but in connection with traditional values. These traditional values lead to a feeling of community and collectivist identity. People strive towards power and status because society rates traditional values and norms. Politics allow room for individual focus and strengths.

The detachment between the individual and the community is met by a style of governance that aims to achieve its policy goals by incentivizing individual and corporate actions, in order to counterbalance the deficiency in society's interest. A new law gives power to stakeholders to participate to the drafting of legislative proposals in restricted cabinet meetings; however, the discussions occurring in these meetings are monitored and steered by elected officials. This manner of legislating gives back a certain accountability and some form of solidarity to the stakeholders. Given the rather individualistic type of society, the legislator, while allowing this dialogue between the stakeholders, tends to retain control of the final direction of the negotiations, also by putting in place processes through which the objectives are set and pursued. Seeking recourse in the courts is discouraged by burdening the judicial system with administrative requirements and bureaucratic obstacles, thus lengthening the duration of proceedings. On average, only cases following an established precedent will be litigated, as the parties are more certain about the outcome and more likely to take the risk of lengthy proceedings. Judges will then in most cases adopt a formalistic approach in adjudication, avoiding having to effectively legislate when confronted with hard, unprecedented, cases. The harshness of social fabric is softened by a legislative and regulatory system with clear, common goals in mind (including sustainability, urban landscape and liveability, technology) although these are a nudge, rather one-sided and forced upon society.

Technologies are widely used for the sake of efficiency and providing equal opportunities for the whole society rather than social inclusion. For instance, automation brings more convenience and safety while it may induce the risk of losing deliberative skills and moral reasoning, which are fundamental for social progress. Policies are also pushing for cost efficiency and productivity of services such as transport of people and goods rather than making them more tailored to the human needs and values.

There is gradual adaptation to Climate Change. Despite the risk of environmental exploitation, we restore small towns and cities in the countryside and traditional landscapes; and reintroduce nature in larger metropolises as well. Self-sufficiency becomes a goal, not at national or regional scale but for each house or factory. Renaturalisation projects are implemented at all scales, from individual buildings, with e.g. green roofs or vertical vegetation, to entire neighbourhoods that e.g. recover rivers from channels. The sustainable balance between individual freedom and environmental recovery is achieved by a more efficient, simpler government, able to implement more sensitive policies, managing emotions and influencing behaviours. People know that their health and wellbeing very much depend on the quality of the environment they live in. Business see externalities and negative environmental impacts as a signal of inefficiency and lack of competitiveness. Environmental taxation, and subsidies to social

and environmentally friendly activities are effective incentives towards more equity and sustainability.

Mobility is needed to sustain social links, social organisations as well as a foundation on which producing economic wealth to be redistributed. Transport policies improve social welfare and reduce the gap between groups and territories in income-levels at the same time, assuring good enough access to services of general interest, and good environment, everywhere. Instead of centralised management systems, and strict regulations, more distributed systems are developed for mobility and energy, inducing changes in people's behaviour. Transport solutions receive little public investment and are liberalised, so large companies fill the gap by providing widely accessible, high-quality and affordable transport services enabled by AI and robots, such as driverless cars. Active mobility and walking also play their part.

5.3.Scenario C: Gaia, the Myth of Interconnections

The potential for change in society is unlocked by a profound renewal of the welfare state, along a redistributive model. Governments are open to societal transformation, and are inspired by the bottom-up approach at all levels. Governments do not perceive a need to correct inequalities or societal injustice through centralised public intervention, exemplified in the welfare state, but explore alternative approaches. An alternative model to the classical welfare state is developed, leveraging on smaller scale redistribution processes and favouring a collaborative approach. Policies are designed to favour the empowerment of groups of people (e.g. as in cooperatives). There is an emergence of 'societal innovation'. The steering part of governance is realised through 'awareness campaigns' rather than through authoritarian measures. The goal of equity is pursued at a collective level, hybridised with an active progressive state infrastructure.

A new economic paradigm shows the results of a profound economic transformation. It is widely accepted that the dominant liberal market ideologies of the 20th Century – grounded in growth, materialism, ownership, etc. – are compatible with neither the needs and demands of society nor sustainability objectives. There is a strong emphasis on the local and regional scales, in terms of economic exchange, and shared social benefits. Equality is a deliberate goal and becomes politically feasible because Europe has shifted towards a fundamentally different economic model, geared towards sufficiency and redistribution and grounded in a decommodification of social interactions and a powerful emphasis on sharing and collaboration. This shift away from neoclassical economic orthodoxy has entailed a marked reduction in global and regional economic integration, however information flows and coordinated environmental governance help ensure the resilience of local communities and collective management. A new paradigm of "commoning" pervades the economy, and the "commons" are seen as a valuable alternative to state or market model of governance in many circumstances. The commoning answer reconfigures our roles so that we are not simply "producers" and "consumers" with narrow economic, material interests, but "commoners" engaged in a physical and meaningful exchange with multiple material, social and sense-making needs. Accordingly, the development of a new business paradigm enforces the integration of social issues into business decisions. Social ethics replace traditional business ethics by offering new perspectives and methodologies to take citizens' aspirations into consideration. As an alternative paradigm, it provides a different framework for businesses by focusing on cooperative and associative models, and providing actionable clarity. Under a pragmatic approach to ethics, the choice for equality becomes self-evident for business performance.

Individuals need to become the most important societal dimension, with self-actualization a significant driver. This development is driven by politics that leave much space for the personal fulfilment of needs. Society is flexible and tolerating enough to leave room for eccentrics. The individual strives towards a "we"-society, where

particularities are respected and combined in a holistic picture. People care about and engage in shaping their own peer group and not harming and respecting people from other groups. This leads to a feeling of safety and satisfying basic needs. In the meantime, many different ways of moving around and structuring the days develop. Goods, highly flexible workplaces, remote studying possibilities, and cultural programs are accessible at any time from any place. A highly flexible, individualized society evolves that is very open for technical and non-technical progress and innovation. Economic success opens more options to express individuality, but it is well accepted that everybody creates their own standards and has different needs to reach them. The socioeconomic context sets the foundations of a mostly wealthy, aware and educated society who supports the whole process against eventual difficulties, such as raising financial costs.

Society stopped being only passively indignant towards self-serving governments and politicians and took collective action by approving a ground-breaking law via citizen's initiative, where it is indicated that a "common good" must be the goal in the management of all human activities, whether political, social or economic. The notion of "common good" gives supreme consideration to sustainability, urban liveability and quality of life. Following the adoption of this ground-breaking law, the legislative branch is reshaped, and, as a first action, the notion of "common good" is codified into law, even though in broad terms. Laws on a number of subjects are adopted via citizens' initiative and all new laws touching upon the notion of "common good", even indirectly, have to follow a specific approval process and possibly needing approval by popular referendum. Citizens, businesses and stakeholders can participate to legislative discussions, they can share their vision and try to "sell" their own ideas and actions in pursuit of the "common good" to the legislator. In this scenario both main actors, i.e. the legislator and society, are active, aware and vocal and have power to achieve their goals. On the other hand, the notion of "common good", even though codified, can be interpreted differently by the different actors, let alone the way to achieve it, which ultimately leads to conflict, usually on very fundamental, crucial issues. The courts see heated discussions concerning the notion of "common good" and any topics surrounding it, creating different schools of thoughts in conflict with one another.

Technology development is envisioned to rely more on social co-creation of value to be delivered to citizens based on the ethical and moral values to gain higher acceptance among consumers. Involving citizens in innovation and development are enshrined in the public policies and legislations. This supports understanding the use of technologies, their acceptance and barriers (infrastructural and operational), revision of policy and legislative documentation and stimulating open innovation, and involving users early in the decision-making process thanks to the co-design and participatory approach. As such, equity is guaranteed for the society's solidarity and collective accountability.

The way we understand nature is not human-centred anymore. Environmental criteria, such as the carrying capacity of a given habitat, become the limit of transformation; not the total land to be urbanised according to real estate interests, nor the intensity of the activities located and the effectiveness of the environmental management in place, such as waste management, but the overall capacity of a given ecosystem to perform their activities. Wild nature not only provides environmental services, but it has an intrinsic value in itself that goes far beyond the interests of current generations. Looking at the environment from a holistic perspective has a cultural meaning in itself. Climate change and other pressing environmental threats are solved by a radical cultural change, pushed by new emerging values.

Mobility is at the core of the political model in the sense of favouring fluidity in society, favouring change, new connections, and new organisations. Mobility is a necessary condition for the spontaneous emergence of new societal organisations. Mobility is conceived in terms of sharing solutions rather than ownership, which is heavily taxed.

Planners and decision-makers no longer consider direct economic efficiency as the main factor when devising new projects, collaborative processes put the accent on new indirect parameters such as impact on societal well-being and derivatives on fair distribution of resources. Reliable, efficient and accessible public transport solutions guarantee free service to most citizens. Informal community transport may emerge as well. In a relational world, the world itself is a city, a unique community, a Global Village. People tend to travel physically in the short distances and virtually in the long ones. There is radical change on values that result from social and environmental awareness and education. We move closer and we use active modes of mobility such as walking, or cycling.

5.4.Scenario D: Hermes, the Myth of Speed

Power and politics drive a dynamic, fluid, fast-paced societal change. But governments do not delegate power to society or to lower levels of governments; they retain power. Policies seek the empowerment of individuals, in a liberal progressive approach. Equity remains an objective but is dealt with at the individual level. Collective organisations are promoted only when they cannot be avoided. In terms of urban governance, cities are supported as engines of economic growth, valuing the agglomeration effect at its maximum.

A change in direction from traditional market thinking demands a more active role for governments to act in the public interest. New indicators “beyond GDP” are championed by various actors, with different status, objectives and visions (environmentalist and activist movements, civil society and local policies, national and international institutions). People now prefer well-being to GDP growth as an indicator for measuring progress. Political frameworks limit the power of corporations. Business is harnessed for the common good. Consumerism is curbed by introducing quotas and restriction in consumption, because there is recognition that material consumption, defined by lifestyles, is one of the underlying drivers of unsustainable trends. Fiscal revenues collected by governments are used to finance a generous basic income. With adjusted wealth and earnings across society, economic and societal paradigms shift to non-competitive, non-status models. The focus is placed on local economy. There is a recognition of the need to transform the ways that society produces and consumes, and an upsurge in efforts to achieve the system innovation, focusing on the emergence and diffusion of new technologies, social practices, and public engagement and consultation in governance. Sustainable finance provides full transparency on governance and fiscal policies. Private property is not so important anymore - due to mobility and flexibility requirements and more travel, workers change jobs more often. As digitisation diffuses into more and more areas of social and economic life, citizens have become increasingly accustomed to businesses and public authorities collecting detailed data about their activities and choices. This information is used to shape behaviours and norms towards more sustainable outcomes, e.g. using choice editing or social scoring mechanisms. Digital community currencies exist in many cities and regions, providing a means to boost the local economy, quantify and manage environmental and social externalities, mobilise underused capacities, and reward unpaid work.

Society is progressive and heterogeneous, where politics provide a frame for individual freedom. Over the decades a more and more global way of governing established and national cultures diminished; and traditional national values lost importance. Individuals make society very heterogeneous with a huge variety of lifestyles. The values followed by people are very much egoistic and individualistic. They search for pleasure in life and enjoy a hedonic lifestyle that needs to be exciting and highly individualistic. This is reflected in extreme leisure activities but also volatile job decisions. People rely on

political regulation of individual borders, so that they do not limit themselves with public welfare or equity thoughts. Politics take care of ensuring as much equity as possible through individual support towards reaching societal standards. Openness for change, new concepts of living and society are the main drivers in this society. Concepts for new forms of work, family concepts are requested from authorities that are expected to uptake international trends and developments in their local management so that the individual horizon is broadened every once in a while. Personal success is expressed through demonstrating competence according to social standards, wanting to be influential, ambitious. The more successful, the more influential the individual is in being part of the development of society.

With some similarity to the Gaia scenario, society stopped only being indignant towards the governments and politicians and took collective action by trying to approve a ground-breaking law via citizens' initiative, trying to set the ground for a more collectivity- and sustainability-oriented society. However, not enough citizens participated to the initiative and it failed. The legislator, aware of the social turmoil, tries to manage the situation by adopting new laws imposing punitive taxation for certain behaviours detrimental for the collectivity and a more sustainable future (e.g., failure to recycle, using fossil fuels) while outlawing others (such as using cars within city limits and construction of non-sustainable buildings). Based on the same impetus, the legislator passes another law, which sets up a citizens' and stakeholders' forum creating a system for the review of certain laws, policies and programs. Once the review is done, the legislator has to review the input and take it into account in discussions. This new system creates shared accountability between the legislator, citizens and stakeholders. However, the larger structural reforms initially sought by the citizens are not implemented, at least not fully.

Understanding how citizens and businesses make decisions and interact with technology provides an opportunity to place the user at the centre of an integrated system. It holds the key to understanding and optimizing the acceptance, adoption and impact of new technologies. Technology advancements are compatible with our individual, social and cultural values which respect the privacy of citizens and prevent fear and discrimination, while promoting tolerance, trust, and fairness (control & protect) in a fluid society. Technologic progress happens almost independently from the control of public authorities, it is unavoidable because it aims to solve fundamental human problems and natural errors. The combination of the Internet of Things (IoT), Big Data and Artificial Intelligence Systems (AIS), powered by increasing computer capabilities creates a second virtual world of global communication without community, with exacerbated flows of data, energy and goods, as well as people, both as tourists and migrants.

Global Change is progressively being solved by the full decarbonisation of the economy, the wide-scale use of electric engines, which are far more productive, less noisy, and clean, than gasoline engines. Biotechnology harnesses cellular and biomolecular processes to develop technologies and products that help improve our lives and the health of our planet.

Mobility is considered under an utilitarian perspective, because of the benefits it provides in creating efficient local labour markets. Travellers and commuters become users rather than owners. Access is prioritised over ownership as a means to reduce costs, resource use and waste. Public and private platforms at all scales, from local to EU-wide, enable the sale, rental or exchange of goods and services (automotive leasing, car sharing). The government intervenes to guarantee access to services for communities that are less well served by private companies, ensuring access to public transport, car-sharing opportunities and driverless vehicles in rural areas. Policies design the built environment and its transport system around users and allow Socially Oriented Technology (SOT) as a driving force to improve the quality of lives of individuals and society and increase the social wealth and individual empowerment. On the other hand,

SOTs are major contributors in connecting and solidarity of diverse group of people with eliminating travel constraints. Europe is transformed thanks to SOTs which impact the livelihoods and wellbeing of its citizens (social and cultural wellbeing) and strengthening the inclusive societies.

5.5.Scenarios overview from the mobility perspective

Table 4 gives a general overview of all four scenarios in terms of mobility aspects. It was built following the activity and takes into account the validations and the contributions provided by the participants in the focus group.

HERCULES	THEMIS	GAIA	HERMES
Growth	Equity	Wellbeing	Efficiency
Useful Mobility	Fair Mobility	Shared Mobility	Fast Mobility
Standardised services	Affordable systems	Collaborative services	Premium services
Security	Accessibility	Proximity	Connectivity
Forced mobility	Mobility shifted to other modes	Free mobility from/to everywhere	Priority to long-distance mobility
New behaviour mandatory because of regulations	Nudged behaviours	New values	Old behaviour enhanced by technologic evolution
Governments are able to adapt transport technology to their authoritarian aims	Transport technology is regulated by governments to a large extent	Self-organization of communities facilitates	Technology solves environmental problems
Assuring reliability	Providing a minimum level of service to all groups and places	Enhanced conviviality while travelling	Saving time to all travelers
Increased mobility coupled with growth. We move more	Mobility decoupled from growth. We move differently	Reduced mobility. We move less	Increased mobility among distant key origin and destinations
Massive	Customized to groups	Communitarian	Individual
Cheap and efficient	Expensive	Expensive and meaningful	Expensive and efficient
Controlled access	Universal access	Free access	Exclusive access
Public transport	Services customized to the needs of users' diversity	Active mobility	Smart mobility

Within national borders	Glocal	Local	Global
Top-down planned investments and regulations	Pro-active muddling-through policies	Co-creation, bottom-up self-organization	Reactive policies
Transport prices decided politically	Getting market prices right by internalizing all social and environmental impacts to nudge traveler's towards more conscious decisions	Prices not being a key tool to induce new behaviours	Getting market prices right with partial internalization and customized to each traveler
National interest imposed by central governments	General interest objectively guaranteed by public administrations	People's interest as defined by themselves directly	Private interest advocated by lobbies

TABLE 4: SCENARIOS OVERVIEW

5.6. Morphological analysis

After the focus group, the consortium members pondered the participants' contributions and estimated the future development of the critical uncertainties in every scenario. Table 5 shows the mean results.

CRITICAL UNCERTAINTIES	Hercules	Themis	Gaia	Hermes
LIFE PURPOSE (-3) Wealth/economic success \leftrightarrow Well-being/quality of life (+3)	-3	-0.06	+3	-1.67
EQUITY (-3) Individualism \leftrightarrow Solidarity and collective accountability (+3)	-2	+2.83	+2.83	-0.83
EMPOWERMENT (-3) Competition for individual power \leftrightarrow Cooperation for collective empowerment (+3)	-2.67	+1.33	+3	-2.17
TECHNOSCIENTIFIC ADVANCEMENT (-3) Efficiency \leftrightarrow Societal progress (+3)	-2.67	+0.83	+2.83	-1
ENVIRONMENTAL SUSTAINABILITY (-3) Control & protect \leftrightarrow Caring/stewardship (+3)	-2.83	+1	+3	-1
URBAN LANDSCAPE (-3) Resource efficiency \leftrightarrow Liveability (+3)	-2.67	+0.5	+2.67	+1
ACCESSIBILITY (-3) Ownership \leftrightarrow Experience/use (+3)	-2.5	+0.33	+2.33	+0.5

TABLE 5: EVALUATION OF THE CRITICAL UNCERTAINTIES PER SCENARIO

6. WAY FORWARD: DEVELOPMENT OF THE REBALANCE VISION

In line with the original project workplan, the last step of the foresight process will lead to the identification, and more in-depth characterisation of the alternative narrative that better combines (i) the most desirable features in terms of long-term sustainability, with (ii) the most faithful reflection of the profound societal values needs and aspirations and of their possible future dynamics, against the backdrop of the agenda 2030 and other inalienable international commitments.

As for all REBALANCE activities, this Task will entail – and rely upon – targeted interactions with experts and stakeholders, notably including a workshop to help shaping and characterizing the Vision, and – for the validation of the Vision – an online survey to gather the feedback of a wider range of stakeholders.

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ANNEX I. AGENDA OF THE FOCUS GROUP MEETING

3 February 2022

15:00 – 17:00 CET

Online (ZOOM)

Time	Item	Contents and materials
10 min	Welcome and project intro	
10 min	Scenario framework	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• <i>How we got there</i>• <i>Presentation of the framework</i>
30 min	Validation of the overall framework	<i>MURAL board to check:</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• <i>Intelligibility</i>• <i>Plausibility</i>• <i>Internal consistency</i>• <i>Diversity</i>
60min	Scenario framework for mobility	<i>MURAL board to enrich the initial characterisation of the scenarios</i>
5 min	Likelihood ranking	<i>Vote/ranking (ZOOM poll)</i>
5 min	Wrap-up	

ANNEX II. FRAMEWORK SCENARIOS MURAL BOARD

REBALANCE Focus Group

Validation of the overall framework

3 February 2022

SCENARIO A

HERCULES

The myth of strength

Overview		
POLITICAL	ECONOMIC	SOCIAL
Authoritative State powers Regional blocs Lobbies	Wealth Accumulation Big companies	Conservative Traditional Homogeneous
TECHNOLOGICAL	LEGAL	ENVIRONMENTAL
Efficiency Second nature (biotechnology)	Empire of Law Regulatory governance	Protect As a service

HERCULES The myth of strength

Validation of the scenario

- Intelligibility
- Plausibility
- Internal consistency

I think under environmental we look - exploit - which is most likely in this scenario	There are lots of things that have been done in the past that we can learn from and apply to the future. It's not about being a hero, it's about being a good person.	An authoritative state power is also a necessary element of a strong and resilient society. It's not about being a hero, it's about being a good person.	Rate of public transport not expected. Not likely to be a major factor of private solutions only.	People do not like to be commanded	What people would like to know, or what they would be asked to cooperate
I don't understand the meaning of regional blocs and how they would fit with authoritarianism	How do we account for differences (Central/Eastern Europe/South etc?)	Why is this model related to efficiency? Authoritarianism is not technocratic.	Is the promotion of technology compatible with homogeneity and centralized power?	Data and prediction should be not based - how do we predict	Is China - Asian liberation, an inspiration for this scenario?
There are different kinds of liberalism, indeed	Creating policy/ products for the majority	Not agile Reacting too slowly to disruptors	Links differences between short term and long term objectives and how they are related to the future.	Plausible because already happens (Hungary)	More plausible policy what the society does I think society less likely than in this
	"Conservative" does not exclude "Liberal"	Where is the space for an authoritative state power that is not conservative?			

RIGID

SCENARIO B

THEMIS

The myth of justice

Overview		
POLITICAL	ECONOMIC	SOCIAL
Nordic type International cooperation Alliances Citizens' involvement	Growth Market-oriented	Liberal Conservative Majorities tolerate minorities
TECHNOLOGICAL	LEGAL	ENVIRONMENTAL
More efficient than social Widespread	Moral suasion Corporate governance	Recover As a partner

THEMIS The myth of justice

Validation of the scenario

- Intelligibility
- Plausibility
- Internal consistency

Why more efficient than social?	you need to make involvement "we tell you what we do" or interactive and "governance"	Whose justice are we "imagining"? Do we see justice for gender/age/class?	The environment could also be exploited in this scenario.		
Is Finland reference for this scenario	I see many overlapping or combination with scenario D	I think there are many similarities with scenario D based on speed	Like in scenario D, I see a situation a combination of soft/hard/just.		
brings more equal opportunity	Could be difficult to distinguish from the Hermes-typed scenario	Nordic type is usually open to self organizing society as in scenario C-Gas			

Society

HARD

Power & Politics

SOFT

SCENARIO D

HERMES

The myth of speed

Overview		
POLITICAL	ECONOMIC	SOCIAL
Liberal democracy (modernized) Citizens' consultation	Cyclic adjustments Assistance Actors collaborate when needed	Liberal Progressive Majorities respect minorities
TECHNOLOGICAL	LEGAL	ENVIRONMENTAL
More social than efficient Level of presence according to sector	Choice editing Social governance	Restore As an equal

HERMES The myth of speed

Validation of the scenario

- Intelligibility
- Plausibility
- Internal consistency

I'm not sure social efficient is the appropriate context... purpose social... exploitative	Something truly "social" will also be "efficient" in the long term.	Could we imagine someone controlling "social" and "technological"?	I've not seen it before than... what about social "technology" hacking?	Define "collaboration" - seems always suspicious if it is not really clear how it is meant	What is the difference between recover and restore the environment?
If it means it purpose then that is different and it not as clearly expressed as it could be	A more plausible scenario would be a combination of B and D	What is choice editing?	Do we account for what is termed as "choice editing" (e.g. non-state from event)	Why does the offering of technological capabilities of the type of "collaboration" - this is a hard assumption.	
INTELLIGIBILITY Does the stress on "efficiency" include a kind of centralized power under which aspect administrative or political? https://medium.com/@thomas@rebalance.org/choice-editing-d6c02a76a274	Choice editing refers to the active process of controlling or limiting the choices available to consumers in order to bring to market goods specifically by limiting things or restoring public choices. The term has general currency in discussions about sustainability. https://www.rebalance.org/en/Choice_editing				

SCENARIO C

GAIA

The myth of interconnections

Overview		
POLITICAL	ECONOMIC	SOCIAL
Shared/distributed power Citizens' participation Capillary New (disruptive) models	Equality Redistribution Cooperatives	Progressive Heterogeneous
TECHNOLOGICAL	LEGAL	ENVIRONMENTAL
Socially oriented In the background	Social marketing Environmental governance	Integrate As a whole

GAIA The myth of interconnections

Validation of the scenario

- Intelligibility
- Plausibility
- Internal consistency

What if generally favor the scenario? It could be so easy to do it. Top-down state powers that can really make things happen quickly	"Quality" can correspond to state-led top-down governance - often it actually needs it	With appropriate tools, it might not be faster.	could happen at local level and have a more rigid gov at state level?	Is Bhutan a reference for this? ...extreme of course...	Marketing is more than just costs or advertisements
Is it possible to move towards more inclusive goals by sharing power with many institutions and citizens?	Utopian scenario/ not really realistic, unfortunately				

FLUID

Type of

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ANNEX III. MOBILITY SCENARIOS MURAL BOARD

REBALANCE Focus Group

PEOPLE 12
TIME 107
Enrichment
Group Discussion

Scenario framework for mobility

3 February 2022

SCENARIO A
HERCULES
The myth of strength

Mobility Keywords

- Mobility for growth
- Outsourcing
- Poor accessibility
- Cheap and ultra-efficient

HERCULES The myth of strength
Characterisation of the scenario

- If you are going to be more specific to what are your alternate modes? nothing cheaper than walking!

Active mobility would play a role here as well but probably as mode of default for those left out

Clean and green energy

technology is a key aspect here

If a regime is authoritarian, there choices may not be the best, but it is likely that transport would be centralized, so no not feasible

Occulsion of violence

I think the use of the word efficiency here is misguided. A mobility system that is not accessible to all is not efficient.

if mobility is not a matter of politics, this could achieve efficient systems, eg electric trams? because they need high volumes of public capital, hence, strong political will

Ultra efficient according to which vehicle?

How can mobility system be characterized both by poor accessibility and "ultra-efficient"? It is not clear that authoritarian regimes outsource. They like to control key infrastructure and services, where friends are placed and usually become very inefficient. All companies Ultra-efficient is not the right word for them. They might be cheap land subsidised to help oligomagic actions and help major economic players.

It is unclear to me whether we have ultra prices or less ultra prices. Could be both, but makes a huge difference.

RIGID

SCENARIO B
THEMIS
The myth of justice

Mobility Keywords

- Liberalisation
- Diverse mobility platforms
- Fair and wide accessibility
- Affordable distributed systems

THEMIS The myth of justice
Characterisation of the scenario

the other point to make about walking is it is the mode for accessing all other modes

what is the role of accessibility in this scenario as the benefits generated by "the car" even as access to autonomy

what kind of changes in people behaviour are expected / likely?

the first three of these above could also be in 'C' - should be!

I thought liberalisation was more a keyword of scenario D

Define liberalisation and consider which segments of the population it affects

It is unclear to me whether we have ultra prices or less ultra prices. Could be both, but makes a huge difference.

Agnt see strong inter-organisational cooperation with Scenario B

Is it possible for this Scenario and the 2 one will have focused developments in different socio-cultural areas? They are not incompatible

"Mobility is an essential part of society" does not characterise this scenario. This statement fits to all scenarios.

The difference with D is the governance of the platforms?

Makes this scenario assumes that the government is wealthy, otherwise it is not sustainable and I am a little out of my league here!

Society

HARD

Power & Politics

SOFT

SCENARIO D
HERMES
The myth of speed

Mobility Keywords

- Travelers as users
- Public and private platforms
- Data management
- Universal access guaranteed

HERMES The myth of speed
Characterisation of the scenario

better streets for walking than better access for young to old, universal access

Are digitalisation trends addressing? Synthetic, data doubling, AI?

Even if "speed" characterising the way of living, do not see the "speed" and the extended scenario description

See comments for Scenario B about constraints and mobility to ensure developments in different metropolitan areas for urbanisation?

Example of self-driving, determined for the collective? How are boundaries of individual hyper-technology?

Space is limited - how are we going to include new mobility technologies?

It is unclear to me whether we have ultra prices or less ultra prices. Could be both, but makes a huge difference.

Universal access should be the opportunity with the scenario? based on sharing and active relations: regularity

Can this option provide better generalised protection than others because power is stronger?

How does public space play a role? How can "universal access" to space be guaranteed in an authoritarian framework?

Elimination of geographical constraints? Is this really needed to be a scenario? Better refer only to travel constraints.

FLUID

SCENARIO C
GAIA
The myth of interconnections

Mobility Keywords

- Sharing solutions
- Active mobility
- Collaborative design
- Equality and common good

GAIA The myth of interconnections
Characterisation of the scenario

highly active mobility and also a role in this only urban mobility? would it be a scenario? Hermes and Hermes as well

A scenario requirement to have active mobility only here

they will be in all scenarios - esp WALKING

if you are going to be more specific than the "car" - search much more thought

I see Hermes is saying the same thing

We will move here, is an assumption that could fit in all scenarios.

if you are going to be more specific than the "car" - search much more thought

How does this link to the scenario? Is it really a mobility scenario? Or is it a governance issue?

Where are the boundaries of individual hyper-technology? How are boundaries of individual hyper-technology?

How does this link to the scenario? Is it really a mobility scenario? Or is it a governance issue?

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rebalance

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